

1 Mapping material stocks of buildings and mobility infrastructure in the 2 United Kingdom and the Republic of Ireland

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21 **Abstract**

22 Understanding the size and spatial distribution of material stocks is crucial for sustainable resource
23 management and climate change mitigation. This study presents high-resolution maps of buildings and
24 mobility infrastructure stocks for the United Kingdom (UK) and the Republic of Ireland (IRL) at 10
25 meters, combining satellite-based Earth observations, OpenStreetMaps, and material intensities
26 research. Stocks in the UK and IRL amount to 19.8 Gigatons or 279 tons/cap, predominantly aggregate,
27 concrete and bricks, as well as various metals and timber. Building stocks per capita are surprisingly
28 similar across medium to high population density, with only the lowest population densities having
29 substantially larger per capita stocks. Infrastructure stocks per capita decrease with higher population
30 density. Interestingly, for a given building stock within an area, infrastructure stocks are substantially
31 larger in IRL than in the UK. These maps can provide useful insights for sustainable urban planning and
32 advancing a circular economy.

33 34 **Keywords:**

35 Earth observation; Sentinel-1; Sentinel-2; infrastructure mapping; social metabolism; material stocks;
36 sustainable resource use; sustainability
37
38

39 1. Introduction

40 Construction, maintenance and use of societal material stocks such as buildings and infrastructures
41 are major drivers of resource use and emissions (Krausmann et al., 2017; Lanau et al., 2019; Pauliuk
42 and Müller, 2014). The presence and spatial patterns of buildings and infrastructure determine
43 societies' future resource use and are hence under increasing scrutiny to inform transformative
44 strategies towards more sustainable resource use, climate change mitigation and achieving the
45 Sustainable Development Goals (Haberl et al., 2023; IPCC, 2022; Lanau et al., 2019; Thacker et al., 2019;
46 UNEP-IRP, 2019).

47 While research on societal material stocks has proliferated in the last years, spatially explicit high-
48 resolution and thematically detailed maps of material stocks at national to global scale are still scarce,
49 limiting the understanding of the role of spatial patterns, material quantities and types (Fu et al., 2021;
50 Lanau et al., 2019). Such maps are valuable to inform sustainable resource management strategies,
51 spatial planning of infrastructure and settlements (Pomponi et al., 2021), improved refurbishment and
52 maintenance strategies, as well as future urban mining and recycling of end-of-life waste from
53 buildings and infrastructure demolition in a more sustainable circular economy (Leipold et al., 2023;
54 Wuyts et al., 2022).

55 The United Kingdom (UK) and the Republic of Ireland (IRL) are an interesting case study for the
56 following reasons. Recent research for the UK suggests a substantial slow-down of the growth of
57 material stocks of buildings, infrastructure and machinery at ~1% per year, combined with strongly
58 increasing amounts of end-of-life materials, as well as substantial reliance on international trade to
59 import raw materials and export end-of-life materials (Streeck et al., 2020). In the UK, approximately
60 370 Mt/year of materials are used in the construction sector, 60% of which are aggregates, 22%
61 concrete, 10% asphalt, 4% iron and steel. In the UK and IRL there is an increasing recognition for the
62 need to address material stocks directly, for example through improved spatial planning, as well as by
63 renovating, converting and upgrading existing buildings instead of demolishing and re-building, to
64 achieve net-zero carbon emissions from the construction industry (Drewniok et al., 2023b, 2023b; UK
65 Green Building Council, 2021). There is also a growing need by professionals in the circular economy
66 (CE) domain to understand the materials that make up the existing building and infrastructure stock
67 to facilitate measures aiming to re-use, re-purpose, repair and refurbish, instead of simply demolishing
68 them. Therefore, a consistent understanding of the spatial patterns and quantities of material stocks
69 of buildings and infrastructures across the entire country is required to develop resource efficient
70 strategies for maintaining and transforming existing material stocks, in a way which addresses social
71 needs and reductions in resource use to comply with climate and land-related policy targets (Cabrera
72 Serrenho et al., 2019; Drewniok et al., 2023b; Li et al., 2022; zu Ermgassen et al., 2022). So far, however,

73 spatially explicit stock research for the UK and IRL have only been conducted for local areas and specific
74 materials (Ajayebi et al., 2021, 2020; Li et al., 2022; Romero Perez de Tudela et al., 2020; Tanikawa and
75 Hashimoto, 2009), or as part of an Europe-wide mapping at 1km² resolution (Peled and Fishman 2021).
76 This leaves a substantial knowledge gap regarding national-level material stocks quantities, types, and
77 patterns across the United Kingdom and the Republic of Ireland.

78 Mapping material stocks requires a consistent integration of multiple and diverse data streams and
79 specific domain expertise. This includes explicit information on surface area sealed by buildings and
80 infrastructure, building footprints, heights and volumes, and, ideally, the type of stocks and material
81 compositions (Lanau et al., 2019; Tanikawa et al., 2015). Sourcing data on the material composition of
82 various stock types at a harmonized resolution consistent with spatially explicit information on
83 buildings and mobility infrastructures remains an important challenge for mapping stocks (Schiller et
84 al., 2019; Sprecher et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022). Cadastral data, official 3D city models and light
85 detection and ranging (LiDAR) data can provide such information (Ajayebi et al., 2020; Miatto et al.,
86 2019; Schandl et al., 2020; Tanikawa and Hashimoto, 2009). However, such data is usually not available
87 for entire countries, or is inaccessible. Additionally, the quality, resolution, and source of cadastral data
88 varies widely, being sometimes based on full 3D light detection and ranging (LiDAR), photogrammetry,
89 or census data. The level of detail in different cadastral data acquisition approaches can, additionally,
90 be very different across data providers (Biljecki et al., 2023; Lei et al., 2023; Milojevic-Dupont et al.,
91 2023). While Night-Time Lights (NTL) are increasingly used to map material stocks up to the continental
92 scale (Peled and Fishman, 2021), they provide only relatively coarse resolution (i.e., ~1 km²), and face
93 limitations regarding their ability to capture non-illuminated stocks such as roads, discern changes in
94 lighting systems from actual stock changes (e.g. from incandescent to LED), as well as saturation and
95 radiometric blooming effects. Recently, these challenges were addressed by some of the authors by
96 developing a novel approach drawing on the latest generation of multi-spectral Earth Observation
97 satellite missions as well as OpenStreetMap, yielding national level, material stock maps at high-
98 resolution of 10 m, applied for Germany, Austria (Haberl et al., 2021), and the USA (Frantz et al., 2023).

99 In this study, we transfer and adapt this high-resolution large-area stock mapping approach and apply
100 it to the United Kingdom (UK) and the Republic of Ireland (IRL), for the year 2020. In this workflow we
101 transfer methods to the UK and IRL established previously, to first map built-up areas (Schug et al.,
102 2020), building heights (Frantz et al., 2021), and building types at 10 m resolution (Schug et al., 2022,
103 2021), utilizing freely available Earth Observation data (Sentinel 1+2), OpenStreetMap (OSM) and
104 national specific reference training datasets. We then derived material stocks information from these
105 data using material intensity factors specifically compiled for this mapping. This way, we could

106 differentiate 9 building types, 32 infrastructure types and 12 materials. We address the following
107 research questions:

- 108 ○ *What are the spatial patterns of material stocks of buildings and mobility infrastructure in the*
109 *United Kingdom and the Republic of Ireland?*
- 110 ○ *What mass of different materials are accumulated in buildings and mobility infrastructure?*
- 111 ○ *How do buildings and mobility infrastructure stocks relate to population density?*

112 2. Methods and data

113 We developed national specific data to map stocks of buildings and mobility infrastructure for the UK
114 and IRL, and adapted a previously established high resolution stock mapping method (Haberl et al.,
115 2021) to the specifics of the UK and IRL (Figure 1) **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden**
116 **werden.** We combined three fundamentally different types and sources of data: (1) Earth Observation
117 (EO) data which enables characterizing buildings with regard to their built-up area, vertical extent and
118 type of stock derived from Copernicus Sentinel-1 and -2 satellite imagery via Machine-Learning
119 methods; (2) infrastructure data from crowd-sourced OSM data; and (3) Material Intensity (MI) factors
120 representing the amount [kg] of materials per unit area [m²] and volume [m³] of each specific type of
121 infrastructure or building, compiled from the literature and primary databases.

122 Our workflow can be summarized as follows (Figure 1): We generated rasterized infrastructure data,
123 that is the fraction cover of infrastructure within a 10 m pixel, from recent OSM vector data (acquired
124 in 2023). We additionally generated impervious fraction cover for the entire study area at 10 m
125 resolution, using a machine learning regression approach, and all available optical Sentinel-2 and radar
126 Sentinel-1 satellite data from 2020, and subtracted rasterized infrastructure data. We composed
127 building footprint data for the study area using reference building footprints derived from the Great
128 Britain Ordnance Survey (Rae, 2017) for Great Britain, which we rasterized at 10 m resolution. As such
129 data was not available for Ireland and Northern Ireland, we empirically deducted a ratio of buildings
130 and other impervious area (without infrastructure) in Great Britain, and applied this factor to the
131 impervious fraction dataset in Ireland to derive building area. We then predicted height for all pixels
132 with building area > 0%, again using machine learning regression, all Sentinel-1 and -2 observations
133 from 2020, and reference building heights from selected counties for training. Rasterized 2D building
134 data and type were merged to derive building volume. We predicted the type of buildings using the
135 same Sentinel-1 and -2 data and a Random Forest classification with manually collected training data
136 for four classes. Material intensity factors were applied to the building volume data according to
137 building type, and to rasterized infrastructure classes. Below, we also provide an overview on main
138 data sources, processing steps and assumptions for each of these sources (Table 1), as well as

139 information on resolution and accuracy. More documentation on calculation procedures and the
 140 validation of results can be found in the Supplementary Information and the Supplementary Data.

141

142 *Figure 1: Workflow used for mapping material stocks in the UK and IRL at high resolution. *... As of 08/2023, only for some*
 143 *small areas exogenous buildings footprints data is available for IRL, therefore we opted for a consistent approach for the*
 144 *entire IRL, which was tested for its robustness – see supplementary information. Figure 1 was adapted from (Haberl et al.,*
 145 *2021).*

146 *Table 1: Summary of workflow steps, key information and main sources utilized.*

Workflow steps	Key information	Data and methods
Impervious area	Machine learning regression using Sentinel-1 and 2	(Schug et al., 2020)
Infrastructure extent and types	Rasterized, buffered and grouped OSM vector data	OpenStreetMap (OSM) processed via procedures adapted to UK and IRL, based on (Haberl et al., 2021)
Building area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GB = Ordnance survey of building footprints • IRL + NIRL = (Built-up area – Infrastructure area) * 0.49. This additional impervious area correction factor was calibrated on UK data* 	(Haberl et al., 2021; Rae, 2017)
Reference height data	Building heights for 25 counties and unitary authorities	(Emu Analytics, 2021)
Building heights	Machine learning support vector regression model using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 earth observation data	(Frantz et al., 2021)
Skyscrapers	Location and height sourced directly	(SKYDB, 2021)
Building volumes	Building area * building heights, simplified to a LoD1 representation of a building as a cube	(Frantz et al., 2021; Haberl et al., 2021)
Building types	Random forest classification and height cut-offs,	(Schug et al., 2021) and table 2

	based on manually labelled training and validation data as well as national architectural information	
Material intensity (MI) factors	Building and infrastructure type specific material intensities derived from national and international sources	See Table 2 and supplementary information & data.

147

148 **2.1. Mapping stocks based on Earth Observation and OpenStreetMaps (OSM)**

149 First, the total built-up impervious area in the UK and IRL was mapped from Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1
 150 data, at a spatial resolution of 10 m with a regression-based spectral unmixing approach (Okujeni et
 151 al., 2017). We transferred the workflow and model developed in previous work for Austria and
 152 Germany to our study area (Schug et al., 2020). Second, we acquired spatially explicit vector data on
 153 road and rail-based mobility infrastructure extent and types from OSM (Geofabrik, 2022). All line data
 154 were buffered with infrastructure type-specific widths, rasterized, and multiplied with type-specific
 155 material intensity factors (see section 2.2. and supplementary information).

156 Third, we acquired building area using building footprints from the Great Britain Ordnance Survey (Rae,
 157 2017). For IRL and Northern Ireland, complete building footprint data was not available, which is why
 158 we first subtracted above-ground OSM infrastructure area from the previously mapped impervious
 159 area, then split the remaining area into buildings and other impervious areas, using a ratio of 0.49, as
 160 in the previously established workflow (Haberl et al., 2021). This ratio was empirically derived from
 161 data for GBR where reliable building footprints were available. There, at 1 km resolution, 49% of
 162 impervious area which is not infrastructure as reported in OSM consisted of building area; the
 163 remainder being parking lots, driveways and other sealed surfaces.

164 Building heights data was generated using the approach outlined in (Frantz et al., 2021). We first
 165 acquired training data from three-dimensional building footprints for 25 counties or unitary authorities
 166 in England (Emu Analytics, 2021), and meticulously screened the data for non-plausible entries. We
 167 trained a Support Vector Regression with Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1 image time series data as
 168 explanatory variables to predict the height of every building in the UK and IRL. For landmark buildings
 169 and skyscrapers, we used the reported architectural height from the tall buildings database (n = 535)
 170 (SKYDB, 2021).

171 We additionally discerned nine different building types. Thereof, we directly mapped four building
 172 types using a random forest classifier previously developed for building type detection (Schug et al.,
 173 2021), which was trained with manually sampled reference data from twelve regions across Great
 174 Britain and Ireland (n = 1616 samples). The four types were Low and Medium Density Buildings,
 175 Industrial, Retail and Heavy Industry, Buildings in Dense Urban Areas, and light structures such as
 176 cabins or huts. In addition, skyscrapers were derived from the skyscraper database (SKYDB, 2021).
 177 Height cut-offs between building types (e.g. low-rise versus multi-story buildings at low overall

178 buildings density) were then used to split these five initially identified building types into nine final
 179 building types, based on architectural insights on typical height differences across construction styles
 180 within the same building type (see section 2.2. and supplementary information section 2 and 7) for
 181 details and satellite imagery for examples of these buildings types). The nine final building types
 182 differentiated can be found in (Table 2).

183 Material intensity factors were developed from information specific for the UK, and then transferred
 184 to IRL, complemented by international information where required (Table 2). These material intensity
 185 factors account for, a) the foundations of buildings in relation to the building footprint as expressed
 186 via m² of built-up area, b) walls and roofs of buildings in relation to the above-ground building volume
 187 as expressed in m³ of modelled building volume, and c) various infrastructures in relation to the built-
 188 up area expressed as m² of covered surfaces per pixel. Furthermore, on the most detailed level we
 189 differentiated 7 components across all buildings: roofs, external and internal walls, foundations,
 190 ground and upper floors, and frames. Detailed information on these material intensity factors and a
 191 break-down by materials, stock types and components can be found in the supplementary information
 192 and supplementary data.

193 *Table 2: Overview of the main material intensity factors per stock type for buildings (MI in kg/m³, height in meters), and roads*
 194 *and rail-based infrastructure (MI in kg/m², width in meters). Detailed OSM key-specific MI factors were used for mobility*
 195 *infrastructure stocks. Values for roads represent averages of key-specific MI factors (High-class = motorway, trunk, primary*
 196 *secondary; Low-class = all other except for gravel). The category 'Other' includes, among other materials, and timber. Refer*
 197 *to the supplementary information for a complete table of MI factors for all OSM keys and additional structures (bridges,*
 198 *tunnels), materials, and data sources.*

Material stock types		Height/ width (m)	Overview of material intensities utilized						Sources	
			Metals	Concrete	Bricks	Aggregate	Bitumen	Other		Total
Buildings (kg/m ³)	Low to Medium Rise Buildings, Low Density (LM_LDB)	<10	–	53	232	–	–	13	297	own estimation, see suppl. info
	Medium to Large Rise Buildings, Low Density (ML_LDB)	10-30	10	198	18	–	–	54	279	Adapted from (Drewniok et al., 2023a, 2023b)
	High Rise Buildings, Low Density (HR_LDB)	30-75	14	250	3	–	–	57	324	
	Skyscrapers (SKY)	>75	34	294	–	–	–	9	337	(Frantz et al., 2023)
	Industrial, retail and heavy industry (IRH)	–	18	26	18	–	–	6	67	Adapted from (Drewniok et al., 2023a, 2023b)
	Low to Medium Rise Buildings, Dense Urban (LM_DUB)	<10	29	257	150	–	–	19	455	
	Medium to Large Rise Buildings, Dense Urban (ML_DUB)	10-30	49	190	–	–	–	16	255	
	High Rise Buildings, Dense Urban (HR_DUB)	30-75	49	187	–	–	–	16	252	

	<i>Light structures (LIGHT)</i>	–	2	147	–	67	–	57	273	(Haberl et al., 2021)	
Roads (kg/m²)	<i>Motorway</i>	33.1	–	–	–	1,470	25	–	1,496	UK and IRL road construction standards, see suppl. information	
	<i>Motorway (link)</i>	11.3	–	–	–	1,534	27	–	1,561		
	<i>Trunk (A-road)</i>	25.7	–	–	–	1,452	25	–	1,477		
	<i>Trunk (link)</i>	11.3	–	–	–	1,534	27	–	1,561		
	<i>Primary</i>	19.6	–	–	–	1,568	34	–	1,602		
	<i>Primary (link)</i>	9.3	–	–	–	1,698	38	–	1,735		
	<i>Secondary</i>	7.3	–	–	–	1,524	30	–	1,554		
	<i>Secondary (link)</i>	7.3	–	–	–	1,524	30	–	1,554		
	<i>Tertiary</i>	6.0	–	–	–	1,538	30	–	1,568		
	<i>Tertiary (link)</i>	6.0	–	–	–	1,538	30	–	1,568		
	<i>Residential</i>	6.0	–	–	–	1,538	30	–	1,568		
	<i>Living street</i>	5.5	–	–	–	1,300	25	–	1,325		
	<i>Pedestrian</i>	4.8	–	–	–	1,300	25	–	1,324		
	<i>Footway</i>	2.0	–	–	–	382	8	–	390		
	<i>Cycleway</i>	3.5	–	–	–	382	8	–	390		
	<i>Other</i>	4.5	–	–	–	1,538	30	–	1,568		
		<i>Gravel</i>	4.5	–	–	–	304	2	–	306	(Haberl et al., 2021)
	<i>Parking areas</i>	–	–	–	–	1,538	30	–	1,568	UK and IRL road construction standards, see suppl. information	
	<i>Motorway on bridge</i>	30.0	–	–	–	516	25	–	541	UK and IRL road construction standards, see suppl. information	
	<i>Box (motorway on bridge)</i>	33.1	217	3,955	–	567	–	–	4,739	Adapted from (Watt, 2019)	
	<i>Other bridges</i>	–	402	2,713	–	637	–	–	3,752		
	<i>Road on bridge</i>	–	–	–	–	276	15	–	290		
	<i>Road tunnel</i>	–	172	4,557	–	–	–	–	4,729	(Haberl et al., 2021)	
Rails (kg/m²)	<i>Railway</i>	12	15	13	–	365	–	2	395	(Network Rail UK, 2020)	
	<i>Subway underground</i>	8	655	13,189	–	–	–	–	13,843	Adapted from (Lederer et al., 2016)	
	<i>Subway ground (bridge)</i>	8	362	4,614	–	428	–	–	5,404		
	<i>Subway ground (surface level)</i>	8	255	2,338	–	428	–	–	3,021		
		<i>Tram/other</i>	7	18	557	–	40	–	–	615	Adapted from (Gassner et al., 2018)
		<i>Railway bridge</i>	12	495	2,431	–	685	–	–	3,610	Adapted from (Watt, 2019)
		<i>Railway tunnel</i>	12	153	4,070	–	–	–	–	4,224	(Haberl et al., 2021)

199

200 2.2. Validation and robustness of intermediate data and results

201 Quantifying data quality and uncertainty is challenging because multiple data streams and methods
202 are integrated, including multiple intermediate data products. We opted for a step-by-step quality
203 assessment, where intermediate data across the workflow were validated against independent data

204 as described in the respective methodological publications (Table 1), recognizing partial
205 incompleteness and differing system boundaries. The intermediate mapping products and methods as
206 well as the overall workflow were independently validated in the respective methodological
207 publications (Frantz et al., 2021; Schug et al., 2020). OSM-derived network lengths for roads and
208 railways were compared against reported lengths in official statistics for the UK and IRL (**Fehler!**
209 **Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** supplementary information section 3). For railways,
210 official statistics report only slightly lower network lengths as derived from OSM. For roads, network
211 lengths from OSM are almost double in the case of the UK, mainly due to local roads. This significant
212 difference between OSM and official statistics, may be explained by official statistics only accounting
213 for public roads and not those privately managed or some types of roads, such as tracks, not being
214 considered in official records. Differences in higher-class roads (motorway, primary, secondary, and
215 tertiary) may be due to varying practices in classifying roads by OSM contributors. Finally, we
216 compared the mapped stock estimates against the literature and find good agreement and well
217 explainable differences (see results section 3.1. and supplementary information section 1 for details).
218

219 3. Results

220 3.1. A map of material stocks of buildings and infrastructure

221 We find that in total 19.8 Gt of materials, or 279 t/cap, are stocked in buildings and mobility
222 infrastructure across the UK and IRL (Figure 2). The highest stock density (t/area) prevails in the
223 metropolitan areas, with their largest concentration in England, especially in the Greater London area.
224 Material stocks are largest in England and lowest in Scotland, where only a sparse road network and
225 few large settlements exist. Stocks are clearly more dispersed in Ireland due to more dispersed spatial
226 patterns of settlements, with only two major spikes in the metropolitan regions of Dublin and Belfast
227 (left hand side of Figure 2). When moving from the national scale shown at 100m resolution to retain
228 legibility (Figure 2a), to the full high resolution of 100m (Figure 2b) and 10m (Figure 2c), it becomes
229 clear why high resolution maps contain useful and consistent information at local, regional, to national
230 scale. Total material stocks of building and mobility infrastructure are displayed in Figure 1a,b for the
231 Greater London and the Liverpool/Manchester metropolitan regions; the complete high-resolution
232 maps of all stock types and materials can be found in the supplementary data files. London has by far
233 the highest and most widespread buildings stock density, while the greater Liverpool/Manchester area
234 shows a more dispersed pattern. In contrast, the density of the mobility infrastructure is similar in both
235 subsets – although underground subway systems combined with road infrastructure considerably
236 increase the material stock density in parts of London. The 10m high-resolution maps even enable first-
237 order assessments of the materials contained in specific local buildings, which is highly useful for
238 stakeholders and actors in specific projects, as well as for regional waste management planning.

239

240 Figure 1: Three-dimensional map of material stocks in buildings and mobility infrastructure in the UK and IRL; with two-
 241 dimensional subsets of the Liverpool/Manchester and London metropolitan areas showing a breakdown into building and
 242 mobility infrastructure stocks. For the purpose of these visualizations and to maintain readability, the resolution of the 3D
 243 map is 1 km (a), and the 2D maps are 100 m (b) and 10m (c), respectively. See supplementary data for the full national-level
 244 wall to wall 10m high-resolution maps.

245 3.2. Material stocks by regions, materials and stock types

246 We find that 17.3 Gt, or 264 t/cap are stocked in the UK, while IRL has a stock of 2.5 Gt or 475 t/cap
 247 (Figure 22a). Taken together, most of these stocks are aggregates in foundations and sub-base layers
 248 of roads at 12.1 Gt, while an additional 4.3 Gt of concrete and bricks are primarily found in buildings.
 249 Metal stocks amount to 0.3 Gt, mostly iron and steel with 0.29 Gt. The remaining stock is made up of
 250 0.22 Gt of fossil-fuel-based materials, 0.25 Gt of biomass-based materials, and 0.35 Gt of other
 251 minerals and materials such as insulation.

252 With 11.8 Gt, mobility infrastructure makes up the majority of total material stocks (59%) in the UK
 253 and IRL (Figure 2). Road infrastructure is estimated at 11.6 Gt, of which parking and other impervious
 254 surfaces account for 3.1 Gt, constituting 26% of all mobility infrastructure stocks usually not reported
 255 in official road statistics. The latter category represents all sealed surfaces such as parking lots,
 256 driveways and other sealed surfaces not explicitly mapped as roads, rail-based infrastructure, airport
 257 runways and buildings. Buildings account for 7.9 Gt or 41% of total material stocks, dominated by low-
 258 rise residential and commercial buildings with 4.2 Gt (53% of buildings, or 21% of total stocks), followed
 259 by high-rise residential (10-75m) and industrial or retail buildings with 1.6 Gt (20% of building stocks)
 260 and 1.1 Gt (14%), respectively.

261 Figure

2Figure

262

263 Figure 2: Material stocks of buildings and mobility infrastructure in the UK and Ireland for the year ~2020.

264

3.3. Robustness and validation of stock estimates

When comparing the results presented herein for the year 2020 with the literature, we found good agreement with previously published country-specific (Drewniak et al., 2023a, 2023b; Streeck et al., 2020; zu Ermgassen et al., 2022) and international studies (Cao et al., 2017; Müller et al., 2013; Pauliuk et al., 2013; Wiedenhofer et al., 2021, 2015); with notable discrepancies only found for a NTL-based European wide mapping (Peled and Fishman, 2021); see supplementary information for detailed comparisons. Using an inflow-driven stock modelling approach, Streeck et al. (2020) estimated 18 Gt of total material stock for the United Kingdom in the year 2017, which includes machinery and other products which are out of scope herein, while the presented estimate of buildings and mobility infrastructure amounts to 19.8 Gt for the year 2020. For non-metallic construction minerals representing the bulk of materials in building and mobility infrastructure, this study estimated 19 Gt, while (Streeck et al. 2020) report 16.8 Gt. In comparison to international studies, the mapped estimate 4 Gt of concrete compares well against UK concrete stock estimates of 5.5 and 5.3 [4.3-5.8] Gt from (Cao et al., 2017; Müller et al., 2013). Iron and steel stocks in the UK estimated herein amount to 0.3 Gt, which is notably lower than the 0.8 [0.6-0.9] and 1.0 Gt from (Müller et al., 2013; Pauliuk et al., 2013), mostly because iron and steel have multiple end-uses not covered herein, such as vehicles, machinery and other products. For buildings and mobility infrastructure, our estimate of 17.3 Gt is about twice as large as the 7.6 Gt from (Wiedenhofer et al., 2015), because of more refined and nationally specific material intensities were used herein, and because Wiedenhofer et al. (2015) utilized officially reported data on floor area and extent of mobility infrastructure, which are known to underreport. Finally, a night-time lights-based stock mapping approach from (Peled and Fishman, 2021) yielded 10.5 Gt of material in the UK and Ireland, compared to the 19.8 Gt estimated herein. We therefore conclude that the estimates presented herein are robust and in good agreement with most previous work, where remaining differences are well explainable. We refer to the supplementary information for more detailed comparisons and discussion.

3.4. Spatial patterns of material stocks

To assess spatial patterns, we use population data gridded in a 1km² raster across the UK and IRL (Schiavina et al., 2023), and aggregate material stocks from the original 10m maps to the 1km grid cells. Plotting those results as boxplots shows that the majority of grid cells across nearly the entire spectrum of population density have approximately building stocks of ~80 to 100 t/cap, with minimal differences between England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland (UK), and the Republic of Ireland (IRL) (Figure 3a). Only areas with minimal population density have substantially larger and much more variable building stocks per capita. We do note a slightly decreasing variability of building stocks per capita at higher population densities, however it is unclear if this is a methodological artefact from

299 mapping population (Schiavina et al., 2023), and/or data limitations in mapping material stocks; the
300 same issues apply to the grid cells with extremely low stocks capita (lower end of boxplot whiskers).

301 Regarding building stocks per area, the majority of grid cells from low to intermediate population
302 density follow an exponential relation with building stocks per area (Figure 3b). For the highest
303 population densities of >5000 cap/km², a noticeable upward increase can be seen, where
304 disproportionately larger stocks as well as a higher variation of stocks per area is found, than in all other
305 areas with less population density. Interestingly, higher population density does not result in
306 (substantially) lower building material stocks per capita (Figure 2a). This might be due to denser areas
307 also containing increasingly more commercial and public buildings next to residential living space, as
308 well as that taller buildings do not necessarily translate into substantial savings in material stocks per
309 capita.

310

311 *Figure 3: Building (a,b) and infrastructure (c,d) stock per capita (a,c) and per area (b,d) in England (ENG), Scotland (SCO),*
 312 *Wales (WAL), Northern Ireland (NIR), and Ireland (IRL). e) Share of population living in municipalities with respective*
 313 *population density. Boxplots represent the material stock in all grid cells at 1km resolution, grouped by population density.*
 314 *Labels of the x-axis represent the upper boundary of the boxplot bins, e.g., 500 for all areas with a population density between*
 315 *400 and 500. Please note that the box covers 50% of all data points, while the whiskers above/below each contains 25% of*
 316 *data points. The line in the box represents the median value. Rasterized population data for 2020 was sourced from the latest*
 317 *update of the Global Human Settlement Layer (Schiavina et al., 2023). For an enlarged version without cut-off at the higher*
 318 *end, see the supplementary information.*

319 For mobility infrastructure stocks a negative relation with population density is found (Figure 3c). Areas
320 with very low population density have 2-3x times the per capita infrastructure stocks than areas with
321 intermediate to high population density, indicating an exponential decrease of infrastructure
322 requirements per capita with higher population density. All regions across the UK and IRL follow this
323 pattern, with IRL and Northern Ireland having slightly higher infrastructure stocks per capita than other
324 UK regions at a similar population density. Per area, infrastructure stocks show a similar positive
325 exponential relation as for building stocks (Figure 3d). In summary, we find a clearly negative relation
326 of infrastructure stocks per capita with increasing population density.

327 We do note however that the gridded population data used above also has potential limitations
328 because it was disaggregated from census and administrative units to grid cells, informed by the
329 distribution and density of built-up as mapped in the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) global
330 layer (Schiavina et al., 2023). However, independent census data is only available for local
331 administrative units, which are very heterogenous in size and their numbers differ by a factor of ten
332 between IRL and the UK, limiting comparability.

333 3.5. Scaling of buildings and mobility infrastructure stocks across the UK and IRL

334 To dive deeper into the scaling of buildings and infrastructure stocks across population densities and
335 test for the robustness of these findings across spatial scales, we regressed building and infrastructure
336 stocks across gridded 1 km² and 10 km², as well as for local administrative units (LAU) (Figure 4).
337 Interestingly, for the UK we find a similar relation between buildings and infrastructure stocks at the 1
338 and 10 km² resolution, with a slope of 0.68 and 0.7 (R² of 0.72 and 0.84, Figure 4a,b). For the LAU, the
339 relationship in the UK becomes stronger with a slope of 0.96, however with a much larger scatter,
340 reflected in a lower R² of 0.49 (Figure 4c). In IRL a substantially stronger scaling of infrastructure with
341 buildings stocks is found than in the UK, with a slope of 1.01 at 1 km resolution (R² of 0.77, Figure 4d).
342 At the 10 km² and LAU aggregations, this relationship becomes even more pronounced, with a slope
343 of 1.12 and even 1.92, with high R²'s of 0.88 and 0.94 (Figure 4e,f).

344

345 *Figure 4: Relation of total building stock and total infrastructure stock in Great Britain (a-c) and Ireland including Northern*
 346 *Ireland (d-f) at a spatial aggregation level of 1 km (a,d), 10 km (b,e) and Local Administrative Units (c,f). These relationships*
 347 *also hold across different assumptions required to differentiate sealed surfaces into buildings and mobility infrastructure, see*
 348 *supplementary Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden..*

349 This indicates that for a given building stock, infrastructure stocks tend to be larger in IRL than in the
 350 UK. Infrastructure stocks scale more than proportional with building stocks across population densities
 351 (slopes of >1), while in the UK they scale less than proportional (slopes of <1). The directions and
 352 strengths of these relationships are clearly robust across different levels of spatial aggregation (Figure
 353 4). These findings show the impacts different settlement patterns have on the required material stock.
 354 IRL and Northern Ireland are dominated by two large cities and the remainder of the island is settled
 355 in smaller villages and towns, requiring substantially more mobility infrastructure. In the UK, there are
 356 multiple large cities dispersed around England and Wales, with very sparsely settled regions only in
 357 northern Scotland.

358 4. Discussion

359 This study presents the first national-level maps of building and infrastructure material stock patterns
360 across the United Kingdom (UK) and the Republic of Ireland (IRL), which are freely available in the
361 supplementary data at 10m resolution.

362 4.1. Spatial patterns of material stocks

363 We surprisingly find that building stocks per capita are relatively similar across population densities in
364 both countries, with the main exemption being very sparsely settled areas (Figure 3). For mobility
365 infrastructure stocks per capita, we do find a clearly negative relation of higher population density
366 having less stocks per capita; which reflects more intensive use of those infrastructures and denser
367 networks connecting relatively more people and places. Less populated areas have significantly more
368 infrastructure stocks per capita, reflecting the need for more extensive road and rail networks to
369 connect spread-out communities. When comparing how mobility infrastructure and building stocks
370 relate to each other within the same area, we find that in the UK higher building stocks under-
371 proportionally relate to infrastructure stocks (Figure 4). In IRL this relationship is over-proportional,
372 indicating that more building stocks within a 1km² area come with a proportionally higher amount of
373 road infrastructure stocks, due to more dispersed settlement pattern in IRL than in the UK (Figure 2).

374 These findings highlight the distinct patterns of urban, sub-urban and rural areas and how settlement
375 patterns shape the amount of material stocks required for buildings and mobility infrastructure stocks.
376 A deeper understanding of these differences and similarities requires in-depth research on the
377 historical dynamics of settlement growth over the last hundreds of years, as both UK and IRL have been
378 settled since pre-historical times and substantial spatial path-dependencies going back to at least
379 Roman road systems can be expected. The historical role of spatial planning, as well as socio-economic
380 dynamics during industrialization and after WW2 additionally play a major role where settlement
381 growth occurred and where major mobility infrastructure projects reinforced existing settlement
382 patterns. Addressing these reasons therefore requires its own interdisciplinary research efforts, which
383 is beyond the scope of this work.

384 4.2. Policy implications and practical relevance

385 The findings presented herein provide new insights into the built environment of the UK and IRL, which
386 can be used for policy-making and planning, particularly for resource management strategies such as
387 the circular economy, spatial planning, and meeting net-zero GHG emissions targets. Substantial
388 amounts of material stocks have been accumulated across the UK and IRL, amounting to 279 tons/cap,
389 with large spatial differences (Figure 2). The majority of stocks is found as aggregates, concrete, and
390 bricks, while metals constitute a much lower weight, however play a crucial role due to the high

391 environmental pressures associated with their production, as well as their economic value. These
392 results also show, insofar available national statistics underreport the amounts of infrastructure and
393 building stocks (see supplementary information section 3), highlighting the need for an improved
394 evidence base to inform policy and other stakeholders as provided herein.

395 The presented maps of spatial patterns and quantities of material stocks at 10m resolution are useful
396 to advance circular economy strategies, as understanding the specific local quantities, compositions
397 and distributions of stocks is crucial to inform local activities aiming to re-use, re-purpose, repair and
398 refurbish existing stocks. These maps also provide a first-order cadaster of potential secondary
399 resources contained in the stock which could be recycled via 'urban mining'. Such information is
400 necessary to inform regionalized construction and demolition waste management strategies, as
401 approximately half of the UK's waste streams are due to building demolition, requiring at least regional
402 management. In recent years, demolition rates of domestic buildings decreased (Drewniok et al.,
403 2023a; zu Ermgassen et al., 2022), while industrial, retail, heavy industry buildings so far followed the
404 cyclicity of the UK economy (McGough and Tsolacos, 1997). Approx. 22 million m³ of residential
405 dwellings and 17 million m² of new non-domestic buildings were added to the UK building stock, while
406 approx. 0.86 million m² of domestic and almost 14 million m² of non-domestic buildings were
407 demolished in the UK (Drewniok et al., 2023b, 2023a), generating approx. 15 Mt/year of construction
408 and demolition waste, 0.3 Mt/year of structural steel and 0.15 Mt/year of steel reinforcement waste.
409 Demolished infrastructure and road projects generate approx. 10 Mt/year of construction and
410 demolition waste, 0.2 Mt/year structural steel and 0.25 Mt/year steel reinforcement. In 2020, the UK
411 generated 59.1 Mt/year of non-hazardous C&D waste, of which 54.8 million tonnes was recovered
412 (DEFRA, 2023). No information whether they were downcycled, recycled or upcycled is available. In
413 2020, Ireland generated 8.1 Mt/year of construction and demolition waste, most of which was
414 backfilled/downcycled (85%), while only 7% was recycled and 8% was sent for disposal (EPA, 2023).
415 Substantial amounts of demolition waste are therefore occurring each year, which necessitates
416 forward looking planning of the necessary institutional setup, business activities and regionalized
417 physical infrastructure for measures aiming to re-use, re-purpose, repair, refurbish stocks, and recycle
418 materials, instead of mostly downcycling them.

419 Because the UK and IRL have ageing housing stocks in need of retrofit to increase their energy
420 efficiency, the stock maps are also important inputs to identify hotspots of potential renovation,
421 especially if extended with additional information on spatially explicit energy use for heating and
422 cooling of buildings. These are, however, not available per building, but only for local areas.
423 Alternatively, ground-based multi-sensor scanning of the heat loss of individual buildings across
424 settlements could yield location specific insights into renovation and refurbishment potentials (Arbabi

425 et al., 2021; Dai et al., 2022), which combined with the maps presented herein, could be used to show
426 the material- and energy saving potentials of specific strategies in high spatial detail. As of now
427 however, refurbishment is not systematically incentivised by the current tax and legislative system, at
428 least in the UK. As a result, many buildings are demolished rather than refurbished, leading to
429 unnecessary resource use and waste generation. As the UK aims for net zero carbon emissions from
430 the construction industry by 2050, the environmental benefits of lifetime extension, incl. refurbishing,
431 renovating, and re-using, need to be demonstrated at a large scale, so decision-makers can be
432 convinced of the relevance of changes in policies. This is reflected by the growing interest from built
433 environment professionals in the circular economy, and understanding what materials are housed
434 within the building stock to facilitate building repurposing and material reuse (UK Green Building
435 Council, 2021). This research therefore provides an important evidence base for planning recycling
436 systems and required legislation, e.g. physical storage sites, transport routes, material exchange
437 platforms etc; as well as for business actors to scope potential secondary resources contained in
438 existing and soon-to-be refurbished/demolished stocks (Wuyts et al., 2022).

439 The variation in material stock types and quantities across regions also calls for tailored resource
440 management strategies. In areas with a high concentration of specific materials, such as concrete and
441 bricks in more dense areas and urban centers, policies could focus on renovation and refurbishing,
442 next to recycling these materials. In contrast, rural areas might require different strategies, considering
443 their spatially dispersed building stocks and higher infrastructure needs, limiting recycling potentials
444 simply due to much longer transport required to match supply and demand for secondary resources
445 from existing stocks. The high-resolution mapping of material stocks presented herein can therefore
446 significantly enhance the design of circular economy strategies, particularly in the context of building
447 renovation and demolition (Wuyts et al., 2022). By understanding what materials are present and
448 where, policies can be formulated to promote the reuse and recycling of materials, reducing waste and
449 encouraging sustainable resource use. For example, regulations could require a certain percentage of
450 materials in new constructions to be sourced from recycled or repurposed materials. These findings
451 can also inform infrastructure maintenance and development policies. Understanding the existing
452 material stocks can help in planning maintenance schedules, prioritizing areas with aging or
453 overburdened infrastructure, and ensuring resource-efficient upgrades, especially as mobility
454 infrastructure is a widely used sink for construction and demolition waste from buildings.

455 4.3. Limitations and next steps

456 Despite the high spatial and thematic resolution of our maps, the results are subject to limitations and
457 uncertainties, particularly on a very local level. For example, while the distinction of nine building types
458 at high spatial resolution is unprecedented, we could only identify archetypes of buildings and

459 infrastructure that likely contain intra-class variation. Based on remote sensing information for the UK
460 and IRL, it was furthermore not robustly possible to discern industrial, retail and heavy industry
461 buildings in more detail, which constitute a substantial part of the stock with generally lower lifetimes
462 than residential buildings. It was also not feasible to assess which stocks are still utilized and how much
463 hibernating, un-used stocks there are. Furthermore, building stocks in IRL and Northern Ireland were
464 estimated using machine learning models trained on the UK, as well as using material intensities
465 derived from mainly UK-specific sources, therefore assuming good transferability (Schiller et al., 2019).
466 Because the UK and IRL have a long-shared history and similar socio-economic and climatic conditions,
467 transferability can be safely assumed. However, for other countries or world-regions, transferability
468 will be more limited, requiring adaptations to the entire mapping workflow given available training
469 data and remote sensing challenges, as well as regionally specific building data. Furthermore, spatially
470 explicit information on the age and quality of buildings and infrastructure would be valuable to also
471 refine the UK and IRL stock maps presented herein, using age-specific building and construction types,
472 enabling modelling regionally refined refurbishment and maintenance strategies and scenarios for
473 future end-of-life materials.

474

475 5. Conclusions

476 This study presents the first wall-to-wall, high-resolution maps of material stocks of buildings and
477 mobility infrastructure for the United Kingdom (England, Wales, Scotland, Northern Ireland) and the
478 Republic of Ireland (IRL), using a consistent method covering residential and non-residential buildings,
479 as well as road- and rail-based mobility infrastructure across the entirety of both countries. Tackling
480 the complexity of integrating diverse data streams and multiple domain expertise into a high resolution
481 10m mapping of material stocks for entire countries addresses the need for improved methodologies
482 and empirical findings for sustainability research. Importantly, these findings can be highly useful for
483 urban planning, policy-making, and the advancement of circular economy initiatives. They contribute
484 to the understanding of how societal material stocks can be managed with regionalized strategies to
485 support climate change mitigation, sustainable resource use and achieving the Sustainable
486 Development Goals. These maps also help identifying key areas for future research and policy focus
487 and offer valuable insights for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners working towards a more
488 sustainable and resource-efficient future.

489

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